

Nutrition of Young Athletes and Their Applicable Requirements

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Abstract:

In the article, the composition of healthy nutrients necessary for the diet of young athletes and instructions for their correct use, the order of healthy eating and the requirements for it are mentioned.

Keywords: young athlete, nutrition, healthy food, diet, amount, calcium, protein, fat, diet, sports activities (training).

INTRODUCTION

For successful physical exercises, not only sports equipment or equipment, but also proper nutrition, choosing the right food is a task. The right foods and drinks are key to being a good athlete and improving. All children should eat a variety of healthy foods based on their nutrition, even children who are athletes.

For this, the following nutrients are recommended for young athletes:

- protein (meat, poultry, seafood, eggs, beans, nuts and dairy products);
- carbohydrates (fruits, vegetables and whole grains);
- vitamins (e.g. fruits and vegetables) and minerals such as calcium (e.g. dairy products).
- meat, cheese, nuts.

Fat is now part of the growing body. Sports children are recommended to eat more calorie-rich food. Because during exercise, they lose more calories than adults.

School-age children (ages 6-12) should consume between 1,600 and 2,200 calories per day. Children engaged in sports should eat 1-1.5 times more than them.

Keeping a food diary for a parent can help a child keep track of his or her daily nutritional intake. Calcium and iron are two of the most important nutrients for children, especially for athletic children. Calcium builds strong bones. These include calcium-rich dairy products such as milk, yogurt, and cheese.

Green leafy vegetables and orange juice. Foods such as meat, dried beans and grains in the daily diet are among the foods rich in iron. Without iron, children get tired quickly. Children who play sports should not lose weight, they are not recommended to go on a diet.

People lose water from their skin when they sweat. Excessive fluid loss can lead to dehydration. Water is the best choice. These include water, fruit juice and other refreshing mixed drinks. Soda and especially caffeinated drinks should be avoided. It is advisable to eat well 2-4 hours before competitions or games.

It is well known that nutrition that ensures optimal metabolic processes, at the same time, helps to develop the body's resistance to the child and immunity against various diseases, increase efficiency and endurance, and physical and mental development. In this, the growing organism includes the rapid acceleration of life, the increase in the number of acquired knowledge, changes in the conditions of upbringing in the family, involvement in physical education and sports, etc.

It has been determined that the need for food for children depends on age, body weight, gender, climatic conditions and time of year. Sport occupies an important place in the life of the young generation. Specific characteristics of biochemical and physiological processes resulting from the action of systemic muscles require the introduction of appropriate changes in the nutrition of young athletes.

When organizing the nutrition of young athletes, the main attention should be paid to the following rules:

- the caloric content of the food ration is in harmony with the daily energy consumption;
- compatibility of the chemical composition, calorie content and amount of the diet with the age and characteristics of the body, taking into account the sports composition and training period;
- a balanced ratio of the main nutrients in the diet;
- use of a wide variety of products in the diet, including vegetables, fruits, juices, greens;
- replacing lost products only with equivalents (especially in protein and fat content);
- following an optimal diet.

Energy expenditure of young athletes is much higher than that of their peers who do not play sports. The ratio of animal proteins (meat, offal, fish, poultry, cheese, cottage cheese, eggs, milk) in the diet of young athletes should be at least 60%, which ensures the optimal amino acid content. The remaining 40% comes from plant proteins. It is recommended to observe this ratio of animal and vegetable proteins in each meal. In special cases, animal proteins can be 80%. The ratio of vegetable oil is 25-30% of the amount of fat, which ensures the optimal content of polyunsaturated fatty acids in the diet.

In particular, the addition of lipoic acid makes up 3-4% of total calories.

Carbohydrates (65-70%) of food and polysaccharides (starch), 25-30% of carbohydrates (sugar, fructose, glucose) should be 5% in young athletes. Young athletes need potassium, magnesium, calcium, phosphorus, and iron minerals much more than their peers.

Children and adolescents who play sports can use the diet. However, their contribution to the total caloric content of the diet should not exceed 5-10%, and their consumption in large quantities should not last long.

There should not be a big difference between meals between classes. The physical performance of young athletes largely depends on whether real nutrition meets the body's physiological needs. Only a combination of a rationally planned training process and a balanced diet ensures the achievement of high sports results.

A young athlete's menu should include:

- natural poultry from plant and animal sources (poultry, seafood, eggs, nuts, legumes, milk and cottage cheese);
- complex carbohydrates (whole grains, cereals, fibers - fruits and vegetables);
- Vitamin and mineral complexes; The diet should contain a small amount of vegetable oil (found in nuts, butter). Thus, the general rules for the diet of a young athlete:
- Number of meals - 4 times a day;
- Their intervals are 3-4 hours;
- Eat before exercise;
- Prohibition of entering the abdominal cavity;
- After a serious workout, you can eat 15-20 minutes later.

Here are some basic rules that should guide parents of young athletes when creating a daily menu:

- The higher the weight, the more caloric meals (children aged 6-12 - 1800-2400 Kcal per day);
- In the composition of the diet, the main attention is paid to proteins;
- "growth" amino acid sources - fish and meat are required;
- Products with a high level of lipotropic substances (cottage cheese, chicken, eggs, fish) are necessary. They protect the liver from fat infiltration.
- complex carbohydrates - the main source of "correct" energy needed not only for training, but also for the body of a young athlete.
- daily liquid level - 1.5-2 liters. The main thing is purified water, unsweetened green tea, fresh juices.

For a young athlete, proper nutrition is essential for healthy growth and development, as well as enhancing their passion for sports.

The main goal of proper and healthy nutrition and creating the conditions for it is the correct effect on the body of young athletes and the achievement of the results of the specified growth level over a certain period of time, as well as the development of the physical condition of training and competition, the formation of physical morphological characteristics, the maintenance of health and other effective conditions, taking into account the correct physical condition. is the main criterion for overcoming fatigue and achieving high results in sports.

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